

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROPER NOUNS IN PHRASEOLOGY

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Phraseology has come to occupy an ever more central role in linguistic studies. It has embraced numerous, often interacting, theoretical approaches and has generated practical applications in areas from language teaching to translation and the production of ever more accurate lexicographic tools. Among the currents of research that have arisen within phraseology, that of contrastive, or comparative, phraseology has seen intense development since the 1960s, although a historical-comparative tradition involving examination of the evolution and etymology of mainly proverbs and sayings, dates back to the end of the 19th century [2;219]. Fifty years on, comparative phraseology can rightly be considered one of the mainstays of phraseology, a rich source of inspiration for research that in turn opens new perspectives for further investigation [3;191]. Nouns are one of the most frequently used word classes in English.

As one of the important word categories in English, nouns have attracted much attention in recent years. However, most of the research on nouns is still in the cognitive aspect or in the traditional qualitative way. The population of quantitative linguistics based on corpora generates many corpora with annotation, which are called dependency tree-banks. It can describe unequal syntactic relations between two words in a sentence [1;16-35].

Generally speaking, proper names encompass several categories: names of persons, animals, companies, geographical places, sign and festivals. Nevertheless, it makes difference in which situation they are going to be examined. In real life, proper nouns are considered meaningless and only they are used for signaling references. It just serves a denotative purpose and according to Nord "proper names may be non-descriptive, but they are obviously not non-informative". As an example, if the name "john" is considered, there is nothing essential in itself and therefore it is in accordance with the abovementioned definition. However, Nord adds "if we are familiar with the culture in question..."

Proper names can make us aware of gender, age, geographical origin. People think that these nouns are untranslatable; Vendler writes that proper nouns are untranslatable, but in the process of translation we can carry them over.[5;124]

Tymoczko also asserts that proper names are indicative of “racial, ethnic, national and religious identity”. In addition, she explains that these names are “dense signifier” and they are problematic in translation because they are dependent on “cultural paradigms”. It is basically accepted that a text based on its culturally specific items would be foreignized or domesticated discussed by many different scholars.[4;223]

Proper noun alludes to several categories: name of people such as hypocorisms, pseudonyms, animal, name of institution, geographical zones, astronomic signs, and name of particular ceremonies in this connection. Every translator utilizes some special techniques to deal with proper nouns in the source text. The definition of “proper noun” in The Oxford Concise English Dictionary would be: a proper name is “a name for an individual person, place, or organization having an initial capital letter”.

There is no doubt that names, in context, make a particular reference. Common nouns, while they can also be used to make a particular reference, always do so through a general property, or ‘role’. This indirect method of reference has side effects. For example, the use of the noun thief in , by evoking a role with certain propensities and motivations, efficiently explains the action described by the verb.

Proper names are noun phrases (syntagms).

For instance, the proper name *Jessica Alba* consists of two proper nouns: *Jessica* and *Alba*. Proper names can consist of other parts of speech, too. For instance, *Brooklyn Bridge* contains the common noun Bridge in addition to the proper noun Brooklyn. The Raritan River also contains the determiner the. The Bronx combines a determiner and a proper noun. Finally, the Golden Gate Bridge has no proper nouns at all.

There is no limit on the forms proper names can take. For instance, personal names in Mohawk are verb phrases. But we don't need to look beyond English to find unusual forms like the brand name *I Can't Believe It's Not Butter!* and the band name the Yeah Yeah Yeahs. Since any string of words might in principle be a name, the internal grammar of names would appear exceedingly liberal.

Names behave differently in dialogue. Firstly, unfamiliar names may be introduced in reduced form (*This is George*). Second, if the name is familiar to the participants in the

dialogue, then the discourse-initial situation is the same as the post-introduction situation in formal genres. The reduced form may be used without preamble – so long as there aren't other, equally salient persons who go by the same name.

For instance, *if you and I know several Georges, none of whom is particularly salient, then my use of the reduced name George is infelicitous. You can't tell which one I'm referring to. I must batten the reduced form with extra proper nouns, or suitable descriptions, until my utterance becomes interpretable. Afterwards, I can revert to the reduced form, since I will have raised the salience of that interpretation of the name.*

Proper nouns behave in a non-trivial way in translation. Proper names, like other linguistic expressions, deal with a host of meanings. That is, the structure of their meaning is basically like that of other kinds of expressions. It is of utmost significance that the status of proper nouns is the function of that particular context; in this regard, dealing with pragmatic is unavoidable. Thus, the treatment of these names is as complex as other expressions. As to clarify the point, attention should be paid to the levels that the intended book, *Animal farm*, has been written. The story can be scrutinized as a political, a satirical and an allegorical or even as children work. Therefore, if we consider it as political, it would fundamentally be different from taking the story as a children work. In this direction the function of text and accordingly the choices made by the translator for translation should be different.

All in all, one of the important factors in proper nouns analysis will be decoding ability. The type of audience will be of greater importance for the translator. The translator acts as a bridge to connect every ilk of people. Therefore, creating the same situation in these two theories in order to saturate the needs of the reader are emphasized. To cut a long story short, translation of proper nouns is of great importance in texts. It is better to sat that translation should be done in a way which is completely understandable either in source language or target one.

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